

LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL FEATURES THAT APPEAR IN THE
TRANSLATION OF LACUNES

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Abstract

This article explores the linguocultural specifics of lacunas in the translation process. A lacuna is a linguistic or cultural unit unique to one language or culture that lacks a direct equivalent in another. The emergence of lacunas in translation is closely connected to intercultural differences, conceptual gaps, and linguistic voids. The study employs linguoculturological, cognitive-semantic, and contrastive analysis methods to examine cultural lacunas in the Uzbek language and their translation strategies into English and Russian. The findings contribute to the development of effective approaches that ensure accurate transmission of meaning and cultural context in translation.

Keywords: Lacunas, translation, linguocultural specifics, linguoculturology, contrastive analysis, translation strategies, cultural differences.

Introduction

Language is the main tool in the process of human understanding of the world, which embodies national-cultural memory, historical heritage, social values, and mental stereotypes. Each language reflects the way of life of that people, their model of world perception, and spiritual and moral criteria. Therefore, the process of translation between two languages is not only a search for equivalence at the linguistic level, but also a process of comparing two different cultures and adapting their unique conceptual world. Intercultural differences are often manifested in the form of lacunae. Lacunae are units inherent in one language or culture that have no direct equivalent in another language, and they create one of the most difficult tasks for the translator. Because a lacuna is not just a language gap, but an important element of the cultural code, which is part of the semantic structure of national identity. For example, words such as “kongil”, “or-nomus”, “mahalla”, “dugona” in the Uzbek language carry a certain cultural layer, not only as lexical units. It is difficult to find a fully compatible equivalent for them in another language, because behind them lies a set of specific social experience, moral norms and cultural traditions. In modern translation studies, the phenomenon of lacunae is studied at the intersection of linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics and pragmatic approaches. According to researchers, the emergence of lacunae is associated not only with the lexical level, but also with the difference in mental models, the different formation of worldviews, and the absence of historical traditions in another culture. Therefore, the process of correctly translating lacunae requires not only linguistic, but also cognitive and cultural competence. Against the background of global communication, the development of translation technologies, and the expansion of international relations, interest in the problem of lacunae has increased even more. Because the correct perception of international texts is closely related to the transmission of intercultural content without distortion.

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In literary translations, scientific texts, diplomatic speech, advertising and media content, misinterpretation of lacunae can lead to distortion of content, loss of communicative purpose, and sometimes even cultural conflicts. In this regard, the scientific study of the nature of lacunae, their cultural roots and translation strategies is one of the current issues of linguistics and translation studies. This article comprehensively analyzes the theoretical foundations of the phenomenon of lacunae, the linguocultural specificities they create in translation, and the issues of developing effective translation models.

This study used various approaches and methods to study the linguistic and cultural characteristics of the phenomenon of lacunae, as well as their specificities in the translation process. The main attention was paid to determining the relationship between lacunae and culture. The study first used a linguoculturological approach, analyzing the close connection of language units with the cultural context, the mental and cultural codes behind them. Through this, lacunae were considered as semantic units inherent in culture. Also, using a cognitive-semantic approach, the substantive and conceptual aspects of lacunae were analyzed. This approach was important in the study of national worldviews, systems of concepts, and linguistic stereotypes. The complexities that lacunae arise in the translation process were studied through contrastive analysis. This method made it possible to compare the lexical and cultural characteristics of two or more languages, and also determined the absence or limited equivalence. During the study, various strategies used in relation to lacunae based on translation theory were considered, including explanation, analogical substitution, transliteration, and compensation, and they were analyzed based on practical materials. Language samples taken from literary works, official documents, and the media were used for the study. This descriptive method showed how lacunae units are reflected in real language practice. The data obtained were summarized using analytical and synthetic methods, which helped to understand the linguistic and cultural layers of the lacunae as a whole. Thus, the study identified the complex relationships between language and culture, as well as linguocultural problems that arise in translation, and developed ways to overcome them.

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that lacunae are the main linguocultural units that express the deep connections and differences between language and culture in the translation process. Their presence leads to certain difficulties in translation, in particular, uncertainties and losses of meaning in ensuring equivalence. Therefore, it is important to study lacunae not only from a linguistic perspective, but also within the cultural and cognitive context. Taking into account the linguocultural specifics of lacunae in translation helps to choose effective strategies. Approaches such as transliteration, annotation, analogical substitution and compensation serve as important tools for fully conveying lacunae in terms of content and pragmatics. Thus, the possibility of more effective organization of intercultural communication in the translation process and ensuring correct understanding between users of two languages increases. The results also serve as a basis for future research in the fields of linguistics, translation studies and linguoculturology. They emphasize the need for further research into the complex interactions between language and culture and for improving translation methods for lacunae in different contexts. In conclusion, lacunae are an important tool in translation for preserving the cultural codes of language and further enriching intercultural communication, and their correct understanding and effective translation are urgent tasks of modern linguistic and cultural research.

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